

Conditioning of Polynomial Regression Methods in Particle Level-Set Method

CMS Research Project Report

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1 Abstract

Poorly conditioned matrices can significantly affect the accuracy and stability of a numerical simulation. Particularly, in particle based level-set methods, we deal with high condition number matrices while solving the polynomial regression problem to approximate the level-set values. In this work, we conduct a sensitivity analysis to identify key factors influencing the condition number in particle based representations. We systematically vary input parameters such as problem dimension, refinement level, order of polynomial regression, regularity of particle distribution and radius cut-off factor to assess their influence on matrix conditioning. We also analyze the particle distributions, to see the effect of particle arrangement on matrix conditioning. Our findings provide insights into optimizing simulation setups to minimize conditioning related issues.

2 Introduction

Representing surfaces plays a crucial role in various simulations across fields like multiphase simulation in computational fluid dynamics, blood flow simulations in biology [1], fluid animations in computer graphics [2]. Lot of research has gone into finding ways to represent non-parametric surfaces, as most of the surfaces in simulations which evolve over time cannot be parametrized. One of the most popular approaches to do this are the level-set methods, where a level-set function $\phi(\mathbf{x})$ is defined for the computational domain Ω with coordinates \mathbf{x} . The surface is implicitly represented using zero level-set and is not tracked explicitly. Formally, we define an evolving surface Γ_t as:

$$\Gamma_t = \{\mathbf{x} : \phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0\} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_d}$ are the coordinates in n_d dimensional space and t is the time. A common choice for the level-set function is the signed distance function (SDF) to the surface, it possess desirable properties like smoothness and it is continuously differentiable near the surface [3]. The magnitude of SDF at any point gives the distance from the point to the surface and the sign tells us whether the point is inside or outside the closed surface. We express this in a mathematical form as,

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \begin{cases} -d_\Gamma(\mathbf{x}, t) & \text{if } \mathbf{x} \text{ is inside the surface} \\ 0 & \text{if } \mathbf{x} \text{ is on the surface} \\ d_\Gamma(\mathbf{x}, t) & \text{if } \mathbf{x} \text{ is outside the surface} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $d_\Gamma(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the magnitude of distance from a point \mathbf{x} to the nearest point on the surface. The derivative fields associated with the surface can also be computed. The surface normal field is given by,

$$\mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\nabla\phi(\mathbf{x})}{\|\nabla\phi(\mathbf{x})\|_2} \quad (3)$$

The mean curvature field is given by,

$$\kappa(\mathbf{x}) = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (4)$$

The surface Γ_t can move and evolve over time, after any such movement the material points lying on the surface remain there.

$$\frac{D\phi}{Dt} = 0 \quad (5)$$

The Eq. 5 holds only for the material points on the surface, but this is generally not true for the points surrounding the surface. The level-set function is no longer the SDF and also loses the ability to compute the derivative fields. To restore the SDF property level-set redistancing is used. Redistancing refers to the process of adjusting the level set function to make it a signed distance function again. It is a mapping from the current level-set function to the signed

distance function, how this mapping is done forms the basis for many redistancing methods. Many methods are found in the literature with conceptually different ideas to perform redistancing. One such method performs redistancing by evolving an auxiliary partial differential equation, whose solution is the SDF. This method is found to be computationally expensive as it involves evolving a PDE to steady state with rigid time-step restrictions [3]. In our study we employ the closest point redistancing approach, where we compute the distance from all the points in the domain to the surface by finding the closest point on the surface to a given query point. The details of how this is done and how the surface is represented is given in the algorithm below.

2.1 Algorithm for Particle Closest Point (PCP) Redistancing

The following steps are followed for the particle closest point method,

1. The surface is represented by particles in a narrow band around the surface using a finite number of n_p discrete Lagrangian particles as shown in Fig.1. Each particle stores the position and level-set values. The level-set values, $\phi(\mathbf{x})$, are initialized using an analytical expression. For example, in the case of a 2D ellipse, the level-set function is initialized as,

$$\phi(x, y) = 1 - \sqrt{\frac{x^2}{A^2} + \frac{y^2}{B^2}} \quad (6)$$

for an ellipse with semi-major axis A and semi-minor axis B . Using this expression, we get a zero level-set that coincides with the zero level-set of the SDF of the ellipse. However, the level-set values do not represent the SDF in regions away from the surface. The level-set values are then recomputed in the next steps to accurately represent the SDF.

2. The next step is to generate sample particles \mathcal{S} on the surface. To do this,

Figure 1: Reference for nomenclature used in the PCP algorithm for a 2D domain [3]

particles immediate to the surface are selected (depicted as set C in Fig. 1) and are used as starting points for a local polynomial regression problem, which is solved over the radial neighborhood of a given particle. This regression polynomial is used to approximate the level-set function near these particles. The polynomial approximation of the level-set function is given by,

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) \approx p_i(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{k=0}^{n_c-1} c_k M_k(\mathbf{x}) \quad (7)$$

where n_c is the number of basis functions in the regression problem. The coefficients c_k are determined by using least-squares regression. The regression problem is given by,

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{c} = \phi \quad (8)$$

Here $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_n \times n_c}$ is the regression matrix assembled for a particle in the set C using $A_{ij} = M_j(\mathbf{x}_i)$, with n_n particles in the radial neighborhood of it. The particles are then projected onto zero level-set using the polynomial approximation. For a well sampled surface, the closest point on the surface for a given near surface particle (particle in set C) lies in the vicinity of it. So the regression polynomial is used as a local approximation to the surface. Due to this reason the selection of parameters for the regression problem like the number of basis functions and radius of the neighborhood for the n_n particles become important, as they influence the accuracy as well as the condition number of the matrix \mathbf{A} . Much of the further studies in the report is related to this regression matrix.

3. In the next step, the closest sample particle is evaluated for each particle in the narrow band. This is then used as an initial guess to solve a constrained optimization problem to minimize the distance between a given point in the narrow band and a point on the surface. It is constrained so that the point lies on the zero level-set. This is defined as,

$$\mathbf{cp}(\mathbf{x}_p) = \underset{\mathbf{x}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_p\|_2, \quad \mathbf{s.t.} \quad p_s(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \quad (9)$$

The result of the optimization problem gives us the approximate closest distance between the particle and the surface. The distance between the computed closest point and the given particle is the updated level-set value.

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = \pm \|\mathbf{cp}(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{x}\|_2 \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{cp}(\mathbf{x})$ is the closest point function that gives the closest point on the surface to a given point \mathbf{x} .

4. The surface is then evolved in time by advecting the particles using a governing equation. The SDF property is conserved only for the material points on the surface. For the other points like the ones in the narrow band, the level-set value is no longer the SDF. So, the SDF is recomputed for these points and then the process is repeated while marching ahead in time.

2.2 Regularization

The initial goal of the project was to extend the particle closest-point level-set method given in Section 2.1. The method described here, has certain shortcomings specially in the cases of violent distortion of the particle distribution the high-order polynomial representation can lead to erroneous, high curvature values. This, in turn can lead to failed simulations. As the curvature is a second-order derivative, the dominant contributors to curvature are the higher-order polynomials. To reduce the impact of these higher order terms, we apply regularization using ridge regression.

2.2.1 Ridge Regression

Ridge Regression is a type of linear regression that includes a penalty term to reduce the complexity of the model. It is usually useful when dealing with multicollinearity, that is when independent variables are highly correlated. It is also particularly useful to prevent overfitting. In standard linear regression the objective is to minimize the sum of squared residuals.

$$\text{RSS} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(y_i - \beta_0 - \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j x_{ij} \right)^2 \quad (11)$$

where RSS is the residual sum of squares, y_i is the response or dependent variable and x_{ij} is the independent or input variable, the optimization problem results in the coefficients β_j which gives the best fit for the given data. Ridge regression follows a similar procedure, but modifies the linear regression by adding a L2 penalty, which shrinks the regression coefficients towards zero [4].

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \left(y_i - \beta_0 - \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j x_{ij} \right)^2 + \alpha \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j^2 = \text{RSS} + \alpha \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j^2 \quad (12)$$

where α is the penalty parameter, a larger penalty parameter biases the solution and the ridge regression coefficient estimates will approach zero.

2.2.2 Penalty coefficients in ridge regression

A classic approach for ridge regression is to use the same penalization coefficient α for all monomials, except for the 0th-power monomial (typically we do not change the y -intercept of the polynomial). Hence, the 0th penalty coefficient is set to 0. But for our study we consider a more flexible approach where we mainly penalize the higher order terms in polynomials as they are the dominant contributors to the curvature values.

2.2.3 Finding the coefficients

In regression problems, we aim to find a polynomial, consisting of a linear combination of basis functions that describe given data ϕ as well as possible. The

weights of different basis functions are the coefficients, denoted as \mathbf{c} .

Regression problems can be formulated with the following optimization problem, here given for unregularized regression:

$$\mathbf{c} = \underset{\mathbf{c}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|\phi - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{c}\|_2. \quad (13)$$

In Eq. (13), the basis functions evaluated at different data points are denoted as \mathbf{A} .

Finding the coefficient vector \mathbf{c} that solves Eq. (13) can be done in many ways. If Eq. (13) is differentiated and the gradient is set to 0, one can derive the normal equations

$$(\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A}) \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{A}^\top \phi. \quad (14)$$

We can use a method like complete orthogonal decomposition to "directly" solving the system $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{c} = \phi$ in the least-squares sense. This method of solving the regression problem is referred to as "standard form" from now on for brevity. For the ridge regression problem,

$$\mathbf{c} = \underset{\mathbf{c}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|\phi - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{c}\|_2 + \alpha \|\mathbf{c}\|_2, \quad (15)$$

the normal equations look a little different, namely

$$(\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A} + \alpha \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{A}^\top \phi. \quad (16)$$

A "direct" least-squares solution without the normal equations is not possible anymore, and hence Eq. (16) needs to be used. The condition number is an important quantity to track here as we solve the normal equations, which generally leads to larger numerical errors as the condition number for the $\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A}$ matrix is square of the condition number of \mathbf{A} , which is already badly conditioned. However, Ridge Regression improves condition number by adding a regularization term in diagonal of the matrix and stabilizing ill-conditioned problems. The condition number of matrix \mathbf{A} is given by,

$$\operatorname{cond}(\mathbf{A}) = \frac{\sigma_{max}}{\sigma_{min}} \quad (17)$$

where $\operatorname{cond}(\mathbf{A})$ is the condition number of matrix \mathbf{A} and $\sigma_{max}, \sigma_{min}$ are the maximum and minimum singular values of \mathbf{A} respectively. The condition number of regularized $\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A}$ is given by,

$$\operatorname{cond}(\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A} + \alpha \mathbf{I}) = \frac{\sigma_{max}^2 + \alpha}{\sigma_{min}^2 + \alpha} \quad (18)$$

For ill-conditioned problems, the minimum singular value σ_{min} approaches 0. From the Eq. 18, we see that introducing a constant penalty parameter in the denominator helps stabilize the overall condition number. This is the trade-off in regularization, a large α improves the numerical stability but biases the solution. Generally, we look for a best α that reduces the error which is obtained by parameter tuning.

2.2.4 Problem description - Simple Ellipsoid Case

The ellipsoid case serves as benchmark problem to evaluate the accuracy and convergence of the PCP algorithm for level-set redistancing. Here, a 3D ellipsoid is considered, whose surface can be defined analytically. The goal is to compute the signed distance function (SDF) for particles around the ellipsoid surface using the PCP algorithm and compare it to the analytical SDF [3]. The level-set values at the particles are initialized to

$$\phi(x, y, z) = 1 - \sqrt{\frac{x^2}{A^2} + \frac{y^2}{B^2} + \frac{z^2}{C^2}} \quad (19)$$

for an ellipsoid with $A = 0.75$, $B = 0.5$ and $C = 0.5$. The level-set values at the surface, which is the zero level-set, coincides with the SDF of the ellipsoid. But, this is not true for the other points away from the surface. The SDF at these points is evaluated using the PCP redistancing algorithm. The simple ellipsoid does not have abnormal deformations and high curvature values, so the regularization does not improve the accuracy and only adds bias that varies with the penalty parameter. To check for the benefit from the regularization we add artificial noise to the initial level-set function.

$$\phi(x, y, z) = 1 - \sqrt{\frac{x^2}{A^2} + \frac{y^2}{B^2} + \frac{z^2}{C^2}} + \eta * H * rand(-1, 1) \quad (20)$$

where η is the noise factor, H is the particle spacing and $rand(-1, 1)$ is a random number between $(-1, 1)$ that is sampled from a uniform distribution.

2.2.5 Results

We do a parametric study of different penalty parameters α , to see if there is an optimum penalty. The mean condition number across all the patches where the regression problem is solved is also plotted to get an idea of the scale of the condition number, although this can be deceptive as the spread of the condition number across all patches is quite large and changes in orders of magnitude as well. We repeat the study for different grid resolutions to get an idea of the convergence. The order of the polynomial used for the regression is 4 and a penalty strategy (0-0-1-1-1) is used, which means that 0th and 1st orders not penalized and the higher orders (2nd to 4th) are fully penalized. An artificial noise of 3 percent is used for the study. The particles are randomly perturbed initially by a factor of 0.3 and the radius of neighborhood considered for the regression problem is 2.4 time the particle spacing H .

(a) Resolution $H = 1/32$

(b) Resolution $H = 1/128$

Figure 2: Variation of Errors and Mean condition number with magnitude of penalization

2.2.6 Observations

From the Fig. 2a we see that for a larger grid resolution there seems to be an optimum α , where a slight reduction in error values is observed compared to the case where there is no regularization ($\alpha = 0$). The mean condition number also reduces with increase in α , as expected. In the Fig. 2b, we increase the grid resolution, we see that the results are much poorer. We find that there is no optimum α and the error increases with increase in α , even if the condition number reduces. The interesting thing that we find here is that, the mean condition number recorded for the cases where there is no penalization ($\alpha \approx 0$) is of the order 10^{14} , but this is expected to be around the order of magnitude 10^{20} . The condition number of \mathbf{A} is evaluated to be of the order of magnitude

of $\text{cond}(\mathbf{A}) \approx 10^{10}$, and hence $\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A}$ should have a condition number that is square of this value, which would be of the order of magnitude 10^{20} . It can be concluded that there is some problem in solving the normal equations, because even the condition number that is being reported is incorrect. There is a precedent to check the solver’s ability to solve the linear system of equations with large condition numbers, which is the case for normal equations. A thorough investigation of condition numbers in normal equations is conducted in further sections.

3 Investigation of Condition Numbers

As motivated in the Section 2.2.6, high condition number problems pose significant challenges in numerical methods. This is also relevant in particle level-set methods, where solving a regression problem leads to a Vandermonde matrix, which are well known to have notoriously poor condition numbers. This issue also arises in other areas of particle methods, for example in Discretization-Corrected particle strength exchange (DC-PSE) and general multivariate regression problems. The operators often suffer from high condition numbers, particularly when particles are predominantly aligned along a single dimension. The condition number of the linear system of equations usually increases with higher order approximations and lower kernel support sizes [5]. This leads to numerical instability and general convergence issues. There exists an ambiguity to what affects the condition number and how much the condition number influences the accuracy of the result. This ambiguity arises from the fact that there are usually multiple factors that interact in complex ways depending on the context of the problem. In the current context of particle level-set methods, we go through the problem that arises when we solve badly-conditioned LSEs i.e. the "normal form" of the solution, then we carry out a thorough parametric analysis of different contributing factors. Finally, we try to give a heuristic summary about what influences the condition number and how the particle arrangement affects the condition number.

3.1 Convergence of badly conditioned LSEs

We check the ability of the linear system of equation solvers to solve high condition number problems by checking the convergence of the solution when solved using "normal equations". We see that QR decomposition with column pivoting performs best for "normal equations", which is obtained after trying out different solvers from the Eigen library (See Appendix). The "colPivHouseholderQR" solver from the Eigen library is used as the default solver for the further studies. The condition numbers of $\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A}$ matrix are tracked to test out the hypothesis that the condition number is being incorrectly evaluated. In the Fig. 3, we plot the error in approximated SDF and curvature with reference values obtained using the method given in Ref. [6]. The error is plotted over different refinement levels, which gives us the convergence of the method. The LSEs

(a) normal equations $(\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{A})\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{A}^T \phi$

(b) standard equations $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{c} = \phi$

Figure 3: Convergence when solving the LSEs using different forms of equations

are solved in two ways namely, "standard form" where least squares solution is directly obtained from the overdetermined system of equations (given in Eq. (8)) using solvers from Eigen library and the other way is the "normal form" where the overdetermined system is converted into a solvable square linear system (given in Eq. (14)). From the Fig. 3a, where solution is obtained using the "normal form", we see that there is convergence up to certain refinement level, after which the error values diverge. In contrast, we get a consistent convergence with a convergence order of around 5 for the SDF and closest point error, when using "standard form" of equations. The lack of convergence for higher resolutions, suggests that it becomes increasingly difficult to solve the "normal form", which is attributed to the high condition number of the $(\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{A})$ matrix. The regression problem is solved separately for all the near surface particles (particles in set C in Fig. 1). If there are n_s near surface particles, then we have n_s different regression problems, which are solved over a radial neighborhood of each near surface particle, this neighborhood is termed as a "patch". Fig. 4 shows how the SDF and curvature error varies with condition number of the regression matrix for its respective patch. Fig. 4b shows this plot when "standard form" of equations are solved. We observe that, when the solution is obtained using the "standard form", there is no direct correlation between the condition number and the error that is obtained for a particular patch, this may be simply due to the fact the condition number doesn't really vary much in this case. The spread is generally in the same order of magnitude. Although, the error itself varies by around 4 orders of magnitude. The reason for the variation of the error in different particles is currently unknown and maybe due to a variety of reasons, one of which could be due to errors in solving the constrained optimization problem. The Fig. 4a shows the sample plot when solved using "normal form". Again, we observe no correlation in the data, but the interesting thing here is the condition number that is recorded has a much larger spread of around 6 orders of magnitude. Theoretically, in the "normal form", the condition number of the matrix is square of the the condition number of

matrix in "standard form", as we solve $\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{A}$ matrix for the "normal form" as opposed to \mathbf{A} matrix in the "standard form". As a result, we would expect that the condition numbers of all particles when solving using "normal form" would be around 10^{22} as it is around 10^{11} in the case of "standard form", but we see that the spread ranges between $10^{16} - 10^{22}$. There seems to be an inaccuracy in the data and we cannot make any conclusion about how the condition number affects the overall error. This is further investigated in the next section where, the way we compute the condition number is discussed.

Figure 4: Condition number v/s Error for different patches

3.2 Calculation of Condition number

The condition number of matrix \mathbf{A} , denoted as $\text{cond}(\mathbf{A})$, is obtained using singular value decomposition (SVD) of \mathbf{A} given by,

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^T \quad (21)$$

For the "standard form" the condition number is given by,

$$\text{cond}(\mathbf{A}) = \frac{\sigma_{max}(\mathbf{A})}{\sigma_{min}(\mathbf{A})} \quad (22)$$

For the "normal form" the condition number is given by,

$$\text{cond}(\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{A}) = \frac{\sigma_{max}(\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{A})}{\sigma_{min}(\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{A})} \quad (23)$$

where $\sigma_{max}, \sigma_{min}$ are the maximum and minimum singular values respectively. Theoretically, the condition numbers are related as,

$$\text{cond}(\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{A}) = \text{cond}(\mathbf{A})^2 \quad (24)$$

This is because the singular values of $\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{A}$ matrix are the square of those of \mathbf{A} matrix. The condition number of a patch is evaluated by computing the SVD of

the required matrix using the "JacobiSVD" method in Eigen library, and then taking the ratio of the maximum and minimum singular values. We take a toy problem to verify the capability of this method, where we consider two matrices

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} -99.6151 & -309.6369 & 2.8341 & 128.3765 & -313.5908 \\ -283.6428 & 467.4962 & 195.7290 & 138.8575 & -301.5875 \\ 177.1364 & -24.5454 & 326.2887 & -67.0536 & 63.7491 \\ 189.4263 & -235.8349 & 431.9125 & -154.5275 & 109.5226 \\ 193.4825 & -332.8055 & -541.1973 & 406.5169 & -375.2350 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} -9.93 \times 10^8 & -3.09 \times 10^9 & 2.72 \times 10^7 & 1.29 \times 10^9 & -3.13 \times 10^9 \\ -2.84 \times 10^9 & 4.67 \times 10^9 & 1.96 \times 10^9 & 1.39 \times 10^9 & -3.01 \times 10^9 \\ 1.77 \times 10^9 & -2.47 \times 10^8 & 3.26 \times 10^9 & -6.67 \times 10^8 & 6.42 \times 10^8 \\ 1.89 \times 10^9 & -2.36 \times 10^9 & 4.32 \times 10^9 & -1.55 \times 10^9 & 1.09 \times 10^9 \\ 1.93 \times 10^9 & -3.33 \times 10^9 & -5.41 \times 10^9 & 4.06 \times 10^9 & -3.75 \times 10^9 \end{bmatrix}$$

They have condition numbers of around 10^3 and 10^{10} respectively. Now, the condition number of these matrices as well as $\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A}$ and $\mathbf{B}^\top \mathbf{B}$ are computed using "JacobiSVD" method from the Eigen library. From the Table. 1 it is clear

Matrix	CN using JacobiSVD	Theoretical CN
\mathbf{A}	1000	-
$\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A}$	10^6	10^6
\mathbf{B}	3.22×10^9	-
$\mathbf{B}^\top \mathbf{B}$	4.0×10^{16}	1.03×10^{19}

Table 1: Comparison of Condition Numbers

that "JacobiSVD" method is able to correctly evaluate lower condition numbers properly as seen in the case of \mathbf{A} matrix, but it is not able to evaluate higher condition numbers as $\text{cond}(\mathbf{B}^\top \mathbf{B})$ is much lesser than the theoretically correct value. We conclude that higher condition numbers cause numerical errors in evaluating the condition number itself, which could be attributed to machine precision and round-off errors. This may be the cause for the convergence issues discussed in Section 3.1.

3.3 Parameters influencing the condition number

In this section, we examine the various parameters that influence the condition number of the regression matrix in the context of particle level-set methods. The construction of regression matrix primarily depends on three factors, namely,

1. Position of particles used in the regression problem
2. Number of polynomial basis functions considered
3. Number of particles in the radial neighborhood

These factors are influenced by several input parameters, including the problem's dimension, refinement level, initial particle perturbation factor, order of polynomial regression and radius cutoff factor. Each of these parameters is

explained in the following sections, followed by a parametric study to analyze their impact on the condition number. Unless otherwise stated, the default input parameters used are perturbation factor = 0.3, radius cut-off factor = 2.4, polynomial order = 4 and the default problem solved is the 2D ellipse.

3.3.1 Refinement level

Refinement level H , refers to the spacing with which the particles are initialized. Finer refinement levels lead to a higher overall particle count and a denser particle distribution. This is likely to influence the spatial arrangement and have an impact on the condition number. We test this for a 2-D ellipse case, where simulations are carried out using both "normal form" and "standard form".

Figure 5: Effect of Refinement level on Condition Number

Figure 6: Effect of Refinement level on $\text{cond}(\mathbf{A})$ for different polynomial orders

From the Fig. 5, we see that the condition number generally increases with finer refinement. However, the maximum condition number exhibits oscillations at certain refinement levels and does not consistently follow the mean trend.

Polynomial order	Logarithmic slope
2	-1.96
3	-3
4	-4
5	-4.8

Table 2: Comparison of logarithmic slopes ($\text{cond}(\mathbf{A})$ v/s refinement) for different polynomial orders

The variability maybe attributed to the random perturbation given to the initial particle distribution, which can lead to irregular particle distributions in some cases. We also see that, the condition number of $\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A}$ deviates from the theoretical value beyond a certain refinement level. This supports our hypothesis that the solver struggles to maintain numerical accuracy once the condition number exceeds a certain threshold. As the condition number evaluation for the "normal form" is not reliable, we primarily investigate the condition number of \mathbf{A} in the next sections.

From the Fig. 6 and Table. 2, we observe that the logarithmic slope of mean condition number of \mathbf{A} versus refinement increases with increase in polynomial order. Interestingly, the absolute value of the logarithmic slope is approximately equal to the polynomial order itself.

3.3.2 Dimension

The dimension of the problem influences the condition number of the regression matrix, as it directly affects the number of basis functions and the number of particles considered for regression. The number of polynomial basis functions scales combinatorially with spatial dimension. For example, a 4th order polynomial will have 15 in 2D and 35 terms in 3D. As a result, the Vandermonde matrix becomes larger, which impacts the condition number. To test this out, we conduct tests for both 3D ellipsoid and 2D ellipse cases.

Figure 7: Condition number and convergence plots for 3D ellipse problem

Figure 8: Condition number and convergence plots for 2D ellipse problem

Dimension	Convergence order	
	Standard form	Normal form
2D ellipse	4.7	3.07
3D ellipse	4.9	2.7

Table 3: SDF Convergence order for problems in different dimensions

Dimension	Convergence order	
	Standard form	Normal form
2D ellipse	2.63	1.03
3D ellipse	3.2	1.6

Table 4: Curvature Convergence order for problems in different dimensions

From the Fig. 8 and Fig. 7, we observe that, the condition number in the 3D ellipsoid problem increases only slightly compared to the 2D ellipse problem for all grid refinements. In the Fig. 8b and Fig. 7b, we plot the convergence behavior for the 2D and 3D ellipse problems to check the effect of the condition number on convergence. The results show that in both cases, the "normal form" fails to converge. Interestingly, the point at which the condition number of $\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A}$ deviates from its theoretical value coincides with the point where the convergence of the "normal form" diverges from the "standard form". This, further supports our hypothesis that the condition number is the primary cause of convergence issues.

3.3.3 Perturbation factor

A perturbation factor is used to randomize the initial position of the particles. The degree of this randomization is the perturbation factor.

$$X_i^{(0)} = X_i^{base} + \delta * rand(-1, 1) \quad (25)$$

where $X_i^{(0)}$ is the initial position of particles used for further simulation, X_i^{base} is the coordinates of equidistant placed particles on a grid, δ is the perturbation factor and $rand(-1, 1)$ is a random number sampled from a uniform distribution. The perturbation factor directly influences particle positions and their distribution, it is expected to impact the condition number of the regression matrix. To analyze this effect, a parametric study is conducted to assess its influence.

Figure 9: Effect of Perturbation factor on Condition Number

From the Fig. 9, it is clear that the mean condition number increases with increase in perturbation factor with a positive logarithmic slope of around 0.43. The increase is relatively low and could be attributed to the stochastic nature of the perturbations, possibly leading to a few particle distributions that are poorly conditioned.

3.3.4 Polynomial order

The polynomial order in the regression problem plays a crucial role in ensuring both accuracy and stability in numerical approximations. A sufficiently high order enables smooth interpolation and differentiation, which is important for capturing geometric features such as curvature. To accurately represent second-order derivatives, the regression polynomial must have at least quadratic (2^{nd} order) terms. However, increasing the polynomial order comes at a computational cost, as higher-order polynomials introduce more terms. For example, in the 2D ellipse problem, a 4^{th} order polynomial includes 15 terms, while a 3^{rd} order polynomial has 10 terms. A higher number of terms requires larger number of particles, to achieve accurate regression. To account for this, we increase the cut-off radius appropriately for each polynomial order to ensure a sufficient number of particles are included. A parametric study is conducted for polynomial orders ranging from 2 to 5 to study the impact on the condition number. To have sufficient particles for the regression problem, we use a higher radius cut-off factor for polynomial order 5. For the simulation in the case where the polynomial order is 5, we use a radius cut-off factor value of 3.1 and 2.9 when perturbation factor is 0 and 0.3, respectively.

Figure 10: Variation of mean condition number with polynomial order

(a) perturbation factor = 0.3

(b) perturbation factor = 0.3

Figure 11: Convergence plots for different polynomial orders

Polynomial order	Convergence order	
	pert factor = 0.0	pert factor = 0.3
2	2.6	2.7
3	3.6	3.6
4	4.2	4.8
5	5.6	5.8

Table 5: SDF Convergence order for different polynomial orders

Polynomial order	Convergence order	
	pert factor = 0.0	pert factor = 0.3
2	0.96	0.7
3	1.9	1.8
4	2.6	2.6
5	3.5	3.4

Table 6: Curvature Convergence order for different polynomial orders

From the Fig. 10b, we see that the condition number of the regression matrix increases exponentially with increase in polynomial order with a logarithmic slope of 11.8 when perturbation factor is 0 and 13.5 when perturbation factor is 0.3. This is expected as the condition number of Vandermonde matrix increases exponentially with increase in number of basis functions. The convergence order increases with increase in polynomial order and the values are given in Table. 5 and Table. 6, remain largely consistent with theoretical values.

3.3.5 Radius cut-off factor

The radius cut-off factor determines the radius of the neighborhood over which the polynomial regression is done. It is the ratio of this radius to particle spacing

H . This radius should be large enough so that there are enough particles to sufficiently fit the regression problem. Increasing this radius increases the region of the particles that are considered, so if the area considered is too large the properties of the local neighborhood are filtered out.

Figure 12: Effect of radius cut-off factor on condition number

(a) Convergence - Radius cutoff = 2.4

(b) Convergence - Radius cutoff = 3.5

(c) Convergence - Radius cutoff = 4.5

Figure 13: Convergence with different radius cut-off factors

Radius Cutoff Factor	Convergence order	
	Direct Method	Normal Form
2.4	4.7	3.07
3.5	5.1	4.1
4.5	8.26	8.25

Table 7: SDF Convergence order for different radius cutoff factors

Radius Cutoff Factor	Convergence order	
	Direct Method	Normal Form
2.4	2.63	1.03
3.5	3.7	3.2
4.5	4.86	4.86

Table 8: Curvature Convergence order for different radius cutoff factors

From the Fig. 12, we see that the condition number of the regression matrix decreases with increase in radius cut-off factor with a logarithmic slope of -4.3. From the Fig. 13, we observe that a much smoother convergence is obtained when large radius cut off factor is used. From Table. 7 and Table. 8 where the convergence values are reported, we see abnormally high convergence for higher cut-off radius. This is deceptive, as when we use a very large radius cut-off for coarse refinements, the actual radius of neighborhood is very large. This results in filtering out of local surface properties and results in inaccurate and high error results. This artificially inflates the convergence as the error values for finer refinements remain the same. From the study, we see that choosing an optimum radius cut-off factor is very important.

3.4 Why condition numbers vary between different patches

In the Section 3.3 we analyzed how input parameters like polynomial order, radius cut-off factor, and refinement level influence the condition number of the regression matrix. However, as shown in Fig. 4, the condition number varies significantly across different patches within the same simulation. The ambiguity of condition number in particle distributions arises due to variability in how particles are spatially arranged, making it difficult to interpret. Unlike directly measurable parameters like refinement level, particle distributions are ambiguous, as there is no straightforward way to quantify how well-distributed the particles are in a given patch. We test out three key metrics that may correlate with the condition number. Namely,

1. Nearest neighbor spacing
2. Discrepancy
3. Principal components analysis

To quantify the relationship between these metrics and the condition number,

we use the Pearson correlation coefficient r , given by,

$$r = \frac{\sum(X_i - \bar{X})(Y_i - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum(X_i - \bar{X})^2} \sqrt{\sum(Y_i - \bar{Y})^2}} \quad (26)$$

where X_i, Y_i are individual data points and \bar{X}, \bar{Y} are the mean values of X and Y . There is perfect positive correlation if $r = 1$, which means that both variables increase together, similarly if $r = -1$, there is perfect negative correlation, which means that one variable increases when the other decreases. There is no correlation if $r = 0$.

The condition number of regression matrix \mathbf{A} mainly depends on the position of the particles, number of particles and the basis functions for the polynomial approximation. Since we are comparing different patches within the same problem, the polynomial basis functions remain constant. Thus, any variation in the condition number is primarily due to particle positioning and count.

To isolate the effect of spatial arrangement, we bin the patches based on the number of particles within the cut-off radius, ensuring that comparisons are made between patches with a similar number of particles. We use the following parameters to get the data, refinement level $H = 1/30$, perturbation factor = 0.3, radius cut-off factor = 2.4 and polynomial order = 4. We observe that the number of particles in different patches varies from 15 to 22. To reduce bias, we divide the patches into three bins based on particle count and compare the metrics and condition number within each bin separately. This allows us to assess whether particle distribution with similar particle counts, play a significant role in explaining the variation in condition numbers.

3.4.1 Nearest neighbor spacing

The nearest neighbor spacing d_{min} quantifies the smallest distance between each particle and it's closest neighbor in the distribution. For a set of n_p particles with particles positions \mathbf{x}_i , the nearest neighbor spacing is defined as,

$$d_{min,i} = \min_{j \neq i} \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\|_2 \quad (27)$$

Using this we define the mean nearest neighbor spacing,

$$\bar{d}_{min} = \frac{1}{n_p} \sum_{i=1}^{n_p} d_{min,i} \quad (28)$$

The normalized mean nearest neighbor spacing is given by,

$$\tilde{d}_{min} = \frac{\bar{d}_{min}}{H} \quad (29)$$

The standard deviation of the nearest neighbor spacing is given by,

$$\sigma_{d_{min}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_p} \sum_{i=1}^{n_p} (d_{min,i} - \bar{d}_{min})^2} \quad (30)$$

We write the normalized standard deviation as,

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{d_{min}} = \frac{\sigma_{d_{min}}}{H} \quad (31)$$

The mean nearest neighbor spacing represents the average distance between each particle and its closest neighbor. When the normalized mean \tilde{d}_{min} is close to 1, it indicates that the nearest-neighbor distances of particles are centered around the refinement level. A lower value of standard deviation $\sigma_{d_{min}}$ indicates that the particles have nearly equal nearest-neighbor distances, which means it is has a more uniform distribution.

Figure 14: Variation of condition number with mean nearest neighbor spacing

Figure 15: Variation of condition number with standard deviation of nearest neighbor spacing

From the Fig. 14, we see that there is no clear correlation between mean nearest neighbor spacing and condition number, which is also reflected in the Pearson correlation coefficient given in Table. 9. In the Fig. 15 we see a negative correlation between condition number and standard deviation of the nearest neighbor spacing for the bin 1 where the number of particles are between

Metric	Pearson Correlation Coefficient		
	Bin 1	Bin 2	Bin 3
\tilde{d}_{min}	0.083	-0.063	-0.14
$\tilde{\sigma}_{d_{min}}$	-0.484	0.138	-0.096

Table 9: Pearson correlation coefficients for different metrics across bins

15-17. But this trend is not consistent in other bins, so there is no conclusive evidence for us to say that standard deviation is a reliable metric to judge the condition number.

3.4.2 Discrepancy

Discrepancy is a measure of how uniformly a set of points are distributed in a given domain. A low discrepancy indicates a uniform distribution, whereas high discrepancy indicates that the points are either clustered or sparse. Mathematically, we define discrepancy as the deviation between the empirical distribution of points and the uniform distribution for a set of N points $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\}$ in a unit hypercube $[0, 1]^d$. A common discrepancy measure is called the star discrepancy [7], and is defined as,

$$D_N^* = \sup_{B \subset [0,1]^d} \left| \frac{\#\{x_i \in B\}}{N} - \text{Vol}(B) \right| \quad (32)$$

where B is a sub-box of the unit hypercube, $\#\{x_i \in B\}$ is the number of points inside B and $\text{Vol}(B)$ represents the volume of the sub-box B . In practice, to compute the discrepancy of a given particle distribution we use the "discrepancy" function from "scipy" library in python. We then calculate the discrepancy of the particle distributions in different patches and plot them along with the corresponding condition number.

Figure 16: Variation of condition number with discrepancy

From the Fig. 16, we see that when the discrepancy is high the condition

Metric	Pearson Correlation Coefficient		
	Bin 1	Bin 2	Bin 3
discrepancy	0.182	0.072	0.071

Table 10: Pearson correlation coefficients for correlation between discrepancy and condition number, evaluated across bins

number is generally low. When the discrepancy is low, the condition number does not follow a particular trend and the points are scattered around wide ranging condition numbers. No definitive correlation is observed, which is further supported by the Pearson correlation coefficient in the Table 10, indicating little to no relationship between the condition number and discrepancy.

3.4.3 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

The Principal Components Analysis (PCA) transforms a dataset by identifying new axes, called principal components, that maximize variance. This re-orientes the data points along the directions of greatest spread. The steps for performing PCA on a particle distribution are,

1. The dataset is centered by subtracting the mean of the dataset from each data point
2. The covariance matrix, which represents how different components of the dataset vary together, is computed as,

$$\mathbf{C} = \frac{1}{n_p} X^\top X \quad (33)$$

where \mathbf{C} is the covariance matrix, $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n_p \times n_d}$ is the data matrix, with n_p particles in n_d dimensional space.

3. The principal components are obtained by computing the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the covariance matrix. The eigenvectors indicate the directions of maximum variance (principal components), and the eigenvalues quantify the variance captured by each component.
4. In practice, we use the "PCA" function from the "scikit-learn" library in Python. We compute the PCA with 2 components, as this allows us a simple way to describe the particle distribution.
5. We then compute the ratio of largest and smallest eigenvalue, which gives us an insight into how stretched the particle distribution is along a particular principal direction,

$$\lambda_{ratio} = \frac{\lambda_{max}}{\lambda_{min}} \quad (34)$$

where $\lambda_{max}, \lambda_{min}$ is the largest and smallest eigenvalues of the covariance matrix.

6. This ratio is computed for each patch in a given simulation. The results are plotted along with the corresponding condition number of the patch, to compare

the relationship between them.

Figure 17: Variation of condition number with PCA λ_{ratio}

Metric	Pearson Correlation Coefficient		
	Bin 1	Bin 2	Bin 3
λ_{ratio}	0.555	0.495	0.19

Table 11: Pearson correlation coefficients for correlation between λ_{ratio} and condition number, evaluated across bins

From the Fig. 17, we observe a positive correlation between the PCA λ_{ratio} and condition number. As the λ_{ratio} increases, the condition number generally increases as well. This is also reflected in Table. 11, where we see a positive pearson correlation coefficient across all bins. This relationship can be explained by the fact that, when the λ_{ratio} is high, the particle distribution is anisotropic, meaning the particles are stretched along one principal direction. This often leads to a high condition number. This observation shows us that the shape and orientation of the particle distribution can directly influence the condition number. We also observe a decrease in the correlation coefficient from Bin 1 to Bin 3. This indicates that a higher number of particles within a patch offsets the sensitivity between the condition number and particle distribution to a certain extent.

4 Conclusion

This study examined how poorly conditioned matrices affect numerical simulations, we demonstrate how it becomes difficult to solve a LSE with high condition number, by showing the convergence issues that occur when solving the "normal form" of the equations. Then, we conduct a parametric analysis as a tool to identify the primary factors contributing to poor conditioning. The

results indicate that higher dimension, finer refinements, increased polynomial orders, higher perturbation factors and smaller radius cut-off factors all lead to higher conditioned matrices. While generally the dimensionality is fixed by the investigated problem, the findings suggest that the main contributing factors to worry-some conditioning of the Vandermonde matrix are the polynomial order and the resolution. An increased cutoff factor can improve the conditioning number only marginally, while introducing significant added computational effort. The main contributing factors need to be carefully balanced, for instance you should use lower-order polynomials for higher resolution problems, if possible. Therefore, a careful selection of these parameters can improve the robustness of simulation. Furthermore, when a simulation fails or shows instability, one or more of these factors may be a contributing cause, emphasizing the need to diagnose the conditioning-related issues. To further understand the particle distributions, we attempted to quantify their influence on the condition number by exploring nearest neighbor spacing, discrepancy and PCA eigenvalue ratio as potential metrics. While no strong correlation was found between these metrics and the condition number, PCA eigenvalue ratio shows promise as an indicator for conditioning of the matrix. Future work could focus on refining experimental setups to better capture the influence of the metrics, particularly by designing test cases where the condition number varies significantly across different patches. These findings highlight the importance of conditioning in numerical methods, giving the way for more stable and efficient computations.

5 Appendix

5.1 Selection of solver for solving "normal form" of equations

We check the ability of the linear system of equation solvers to solve high condition number problems by checking the convergence of the solution when solved using "normal form". Different solvers from the Eigen library are used to check this. From the Fig. 18 we see that, there is marked difference in convergence when using different solvers. When using QR decomposition with full pivoting there is no convergence observed. The solver using QR decomposition with column pivoting performs better and there is convergence up to certain refinement level, after which error values diverge. We see that QR decomposition with column pivoting performs best for normal equations and is used as the default solver for the simulations.

Figure 18: Convergence plot when normal equations are used $(\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{A})\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{A}^T \phi$

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